

**LIBRARY SERVICES FOR THE PHYSICALLY CHALLENGED USERS
OF THE PUBLIC LIBRARIES IN PURBA MEDINIPUR, PASCHIM
MEDINIPUR AND JHARGRAM DISTRICT**

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Abstract: Differently abled is a term for someone who might formerly have been classed as disabled, handicapped, challenged, or having special needs. It can apply to people with predominantly physical or mental challenges. The description is thought to be more politically correct in some circles because it recognizes that even if people have mental and/or physical impairments, they still have abilities, contrary to the picture painted with the terms disabled or handicapped. This study focuses on the library services provide by the public libraries for differently abled users. This study tries to depict the picture of the technologies and software that are useful in providing the services to the differently-abled users. This study reveals the strengths and weaknesses of the public libraries in West Bengal serving the people with various disabilities namely blindness, low vision, hearing difficulties, mobility problems, etc.

Keywords: Differently-abled Person, Library Service, Access of Library Resources, Public Libraries

Introduction: The United Nations (UN) defines disability as a broad umbrella term that can be conceived in two parts. Disabilities are “long-term physical, mental, intellectual or sensory impairments which, in interaction with various attitudinal and environmental barriers, hinders full and effective participation in society” (2009).

The Persons with Disability People are neglected, jaunty, disrespected, and harassed in every sectors of our society due to lack of right information, proper education, right communication, rules and regulations enactment and implementation. They have also equal right and opportunity of all other human beings. The Differently able people are integral part as well as wealth in our society. They also want to serve our society as well as our country by their efficient effort. But their present socioeconomic position, background, education, employment, life struggle, etc. are different from other normal people. So, overcome the differences which they face in their own life, they necessity information from various sources of our society i.e., public libraries, school libraries, college libraries and university libraries, to make their life styles. Every citizen included the disabilities people of the society have provision of the right to information and right to education. Its means directly or indirectly

they can solve problems and make decision of their daily life. The main goal of Government sponsored public libraries is to satisfy their physically challenged of user's information needs and library services through their proper valuable traditional with digital resources.

What is Disability?

The term "disability" is an acronym derived from the English phrase "Different Ability", which after absorption into disabled or people with disability. This term appears based on the reality that every human is created differently so they have different abilities. The word was change into "people with disability" to reduce negative impression and discrimination, and besides that, it is conformed that shows no defects but only a difference. Changing the label of people with disability into people with different ability not only change the terms, but also alters the meaning of the recognition of the capabilities of an individual who has a physical condition (body) different from the others. This change was made in order to gradually change the public opinion, that the disability is demand not to have benefit for life and just burden to the normal.

Physically Challenged: Lawal-Solarin (2010) in an article titled Banks and the Physically Challenged quoted MSN Encarta Dictionary which defines physically challenged as an inability to perform some or all the tasks of daily life or a medically diagnosed condition that makes it difficult to engage in the activities of daily life. According to the World Book Encyclopedia (2004), "some people are born with disabilities, while others develop them later in life. There are however, many types of challenges or disabilities; both physical and mental, and they vary greatly in causes, degrees and treatments. Common disabilities include blindness, deafness, and deformity, loss of limbs, mental illness, mental retardation, muscular, nervous and sensory disorders".

Assistive Technology:

Assistive Services for Blind Users:

Public libraries can provide library services to visually challenged using various tools and techniques. Some of them are listed below:

- i) JAWS Pro Talking Software: Jaws Pro Talking software is used for converting a normal PC into a talking PC enabling visually-impaired users to operate computers independently including Internet Access. The software also trains visually-impaired persons on using the computer.
- ii) Kurzweil 1000 OCR Reading Software: The software provides excellent support to blind people in reading any printed book from the library without help of a volunteer reader. The software is used in combination of a scanner and a PC.
- iii) Magic Magnification Software Pro: The software is useful for enlarging the screen from 2x to 16x enabling users with low vision to view the monitor screen as well as use the add-on support tools for enhancing visibility.

iv) Talking Typing Teacher Pro: Talking Typing Teacher Pro is specially designed for assisting blind in learning keyboarding skills and gaining typing speed in a systematic manner. The software comes with complete guidance and practice lessons. Since the program also has a complete display of all lessons, even the people with low vision can read and learn to type.

v) Braille Scanning Software – OBR (Optical Braille Recognition): Optical Braille Recognition (OBR) is a Windows-based software program that allows users to ‘read’ single- and double-sided Braille documents on a standard A4 scanner. It scans the Braille document, analyses the dot pattern, and translates it into normal text that it presents on the computer screen.

Assistive Services for Deaf & Dumb:

The following assistive services can be offered to users with speech and hearing disability:

- i) Information in sign language or displaying videos
- ii) Information via text telephones and/or email
- iii) Information through the library’s accessible website (audio information should also be available as text)
- iv) Easy-to-read text for patrons who were born deaf or became deaf before acquiring language skills

Assistive Services for Persons with Reading Difficulties:

The following assistive services can be offered to users with reading disability:

- i) Information written in an easy-to-read text
- ii) Information via audio/video tape, CD/DVD, or in Daisy format
- iii) Information through the library’s website

Assistive Services for persons with Physical Disabilities:

The following assistive services can be offered to users with physical disability:

- i) Information on audio/video tape or on CD/DVD or in DAISY format
- ii) Information through library’s website

Assistive Services for Cognitively Disabled Persons:

The following assistive services can be offered to users with cognitively disabled persons:

- i) Information in an easy-to-read format

ii) Information via audio/video tape, CD/DVD, or in DAISY format

iii) Information through the library's website

Types of disabilities:

The concept of 'Disability' needs to be redefined in the light of the paradigm shift that has taken place in recognizing the rights of persons with disabilities. "Policy has now shifted towards community and educational inclusion, and medically-focused solutions have given way to more interactive approaches recognizing that people are disabled by environmental factors as well as by their bodies." (WHO, 2011)

There are many types of disabilities, such as those that affect a person's

- Vision
- Movement
- Thinking
- Remembering
- Learning
- Communicating
- Hearing
- Mental health and
- Social relationship

Public Library: Dr. S.R. Ranganathan defines a public library as "an institution maintained for and by the community primarily for the social purpose of providing easy opportunity for self-education throughout life of every person and community" (Ranganathan, 1948).

Public Libraries in India may be broadly classified into two categories; viz. (i) Government (ii) Non-Government. The Government Libraries though may not be essentially established under the "mandate of law", are mostly free libraries. Some of these, however, may charge a nominal amount as membership or/and deposit money, entitling the members to borrow material for home reading. Nongovernment libraries are run by various organizations / trusts / institutions, etc.

According to the report of Advisory Committee for Libraries of India, the internationally accepted definition of public library is that it is a library (a) which is financed for the most part out of public funds; (b) which charges no fees from the readers and yet is open for full use by the public without distinction of caste, creed and sex; (c) which is intended as an auxiliary educational institution providing a means of self-education; (d) which houses learning materials giving reliable information freely and without partiality or prejudice on as wide a variety of subjects as will satisfy the interests of the readers".

The problem of study: After a thorough review of number of existing literatures on the area of public library services offered for the physically challenged users it is found that no such work has been done in the selected geographical jurisdiction of West Bengal. Hence, an attempt for further investigation has been carried out to identify the current status, facilities and services that are being provided by the public libraries in the selected regions. The study mainly focuses on the library services for the Physically Challenged users of Public Libraries in Purba Medinipur, Paschim Medinipur and Jhargram District. The study is intended to bring out the gaps between the current status of the public library services and the services ideally needed to fulfil the requirements of the uses who belong to the PWD categories. The study aims at to focus on the existing pattern of library services for the physically Challenged users which include 11 categories i.e. mainly Visually Handicapped (VH), Hearing Handicapped (HH) and Orthopaedic Handicapped (OH) or Locomotors Disability (LD) etc. of Public Libraries, availability of infrastructure and number of user-friendly guides for the special users, satisfaction level of all types of Physical with disability users of the society, the use of modern ICT enabled tools for such users, the frequency of visiting such users to the public libraries and to identify the Acts, rules, policies formulated by the Government and initiatives taken by the authorities for providing better services to the Physically challenge users.

Objective of the study: The objectives of the research study are the in-depth assessment of the performance and efficacy of the Public Library Services that are catered to the different types of Physically Challenged users which include illiterate, businessman, Farmers, student, scholar, employee, staff, and teacher etc. of in Paschim Medinipur, Purba Medinipur and Jhargram District.

1. To find out the availability of library and information services offered to PWD in Public libraries in Purba Medinipur, Paschim Medinipur and Jhargram district.
2. To identify the physical environment, infrastructural requirements of PWD in public libraries in Purba Medinipur, Paschim Medinipur and Jhargram district.
3. To examine the availability of information materials and service provided for the physically challenged users in public libraries in Purba Medinipur, Paschim Medinipur and Jhargram district
4. To examine the extent of satisfaction by the physically challenged users with library and information services.
5. To analyse and evaluate the present status, activities and Government facilities for different able users.
6. To suggest some possible measures to overcome the barriers faced by the libraries in implementing the facilities for these specific types of users.

Scope: The scope of the present study to start with confines to Library Services for the Physically Challenged users of Public Libraries in Purba Medinipur, Paschim Medinipur and Jhargram District of West Bengal. The present study mainly covers Library services for the physically challenged users of public libraries, their information needs and source providers including automation and other infrastructural facilities. The study includes in its ambit District libraries, Sub-divisional libraries, Town libraries and rural libraries in Purba Medinipur, Paschim Medinipur and Jhargram District.

Hypothesis: The term ‘hypothesis has two constituent parts: “hypo” means less than and ‘thesis’ denotes proposition to be maintained or proved. So, hypothesis may be said to mean less than or less certain than thesis. The hypothesis of this study are:

1. The available information services at access points of the public libraries are not enough to meet the needs of physically challenged people.
2. Majority of rural public library physically challenged users’ dose not consult a librarian as a information is available for physically challenged people.

Methodology: To conduct this kind of descriptive research process requires a variety of survey methods or techniques such as research methods, interview methods and observation methods were used as instruments to collect data.

The Study used a survey questionnaire. A questionnaire was prepared after comprehensive literature search and discussion with subject experts. Both open and closed question were included in the questionnaire. The population of the study consists of rural and urban area of Purba Medinipur, Paschim Medinipur and Jhargram District.

The survey instrument consisted of 2 section namely-section A and section B with 31 question. The first part of the Section “A” dealt with the library details of respondents such as library name, address, types of libraries, Facilities for especially abled person, Mode of Acquisition of Books, Collection of Books and Periodicals, Special Collection for especially abled persons, Library staff.

The Section “B” dealt with the library users of respondents such as his name, job position, gender, age group, academic qualification, facilities, e collection of resources.

Sampling:

Identification of Physically Challenged users: The Physically Challenged users were interviewed outside the public libraries of thirty public library in Purba Medinipur, Paschim Medinipur and Jhargram District. Results of the pilot study showed that the respondents were able to understand the questions properly and their responses were interpretable.

Identification of public libraries: Thirty Public libraries were identified for this study. The list of thirty public libraries was selected by random sampling method.

Result analysis: This study was carried out using the thirty libraries in the three districts situated in the state of West Bengal namely district of Paschim Medinipur, Purba Medinipur and Jhargram. This present study uses Questionnaire, interview and Observation methods to the 141 respondents with 150 questionnaires, analyses the result retrieved from despondence.

Table 1

Distribution and respondent age group in the libraries

Age	Frequency	Percent
0-15	36	25.6
16-25	70	49.7
26-35	30	21.2
Others	05	3.5
Total	141	100

Table 1 shows that 36 respondents representing (25.6) are between the age group of 0 to 15 years, 70(49.7%) are between the age of 16 to 25 years, 30(21.2%) are between the age of 26 to 35 years and only 5(3.5%) is above the age of 35 years.

Table 2

Distribution of Persons with Disabilities users according to Gender

Gender	Frequency	Percent
Male	123	87.2
Female	18	12.8
Total	141	100

Table 2 shows that the gender of the respondents 123 (87.2%) are male while 18 (12.8%) are female.

Table 3

Types of disabilities users in the libraries

Type of disability	Frequency	Percent
OH	97	68.8
HH	05	3.5
VH	39	27.7
Others	0	0
Total	141	100

Table 3 shows that the result on the type of disability of the respondents reveal that 97(68.8%) are Orthopaedic Handicapped, 5(3.5%) are hearing impaired while the remaining 39(27.7%) are Visual Handicapped, while others disability has no respondents.

Table 4**Information Resources Available in the Public Libraries for the Physically Challenged users in Paschim Medinipur, Purba Medinipur and Jhargram District**

Information Resources Available	Provided	Not Provided
Text books	yes	
Braille books		no
Audio book		no
DVD and Video (for the deaf)		no
Computers	yes	
General Scanner with software CCTV Magnifying aid unit	yes	
Reference books	yes	
New papers	yes	
Periodicals	yes	
Internet	yes	

Table 4 shows that Text books, Computers, Scanner, Reference books, New Papers, periodicals, Internet etc. were provided by these libraries. Braille books, Audio book, DVD and Video were provided by these libraries.

Table 5**Physical Access to Buildings**

Physical Access	Provided	Not Provided
Ramps		no
Lift		no
Cleanliness	yes	
Entrance with suitable clear opening doors	yes	
Public service desks	yes	
Accessible Public areas such as toilets	yes	

Table 5 shows that Ramps and Lift were not provided by these libraries. Cleanliness, Entrance with suitable opening doors, Public Service desks and Accessible Public areas such as toilets were provided by these libraries.

Discussion: The present study discusses the infrastructural facilities, professional behaviors, availability of information sources and services of the leading performance of Govt. Sponsored public libraries. The thirty Government Sponsored Public Libraries play eventual role in meeting the information needs of their users, especially for empowerment, establishment and development of the physical with disability user's category. The process of categorization of the expensive collections of traditional and digital sources and services of Libraries is also analyzed. The availability and accessibility of the Govt. Sponsored Libraries, Government Acts, Policy, Schemes, Rules and Regulations related information, information regarding equal opportunities, protection of right and full participation of physically Challenged users are also highlighted.

- a) Communication and Accessibility to total Physical with disability user's category.
- b) Library services of physically challenged users.
- c) Infrastructure facilities of public libraries to their physically challenged users.
- d) Government Sponsored Public Libraries Sources and Services for Physically Challenged users.
- e) The different abled person's awareness activities provided by the libraries.
- f) User's perceptions on support services provided at their respective Govt. Sponsored Public Libraries.
- g) Barriers faced by Physically Challenged users in public libraries.

Conclusion: The Public Libraries are the many sources and services centre of information. The success of any Govt. Sponsored Public Libraries depends upon the availability of Information, accessibility of resources towards the right users. Through Public libraries have provision and guideline of IFLA, RRRLF, NKC and UNESCO Manifesto for access to all including the Physically Challenged users. The Govt. Sponsored Public Libraries to provide barrier free services with the existing infrastructural facilities, availability of information sources to diverse population irrespective of their physically inaccuracy. The Library Professional are unconscious about the physically with disabilities peoples. The libraries are not well equid towards empowerment of the PWD users in the age of advanced ICT.

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